

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

MATRIX OF FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLES AND METHODS IN ACQUIRING VOCABULARY AND GRAMMAR OF A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

The article explores the process of acquiring a foreign language, emphasizing the differences between natural and conscious learning. Two stages contribute to the acquisition of the native language: spoken language in the family environment and written language with an academic focus at school. Similarly, one can acquire a foreign language either through immersion in a language environment or through intensive instruction with a teacher. Natural acquisition is more effective, but the intensive learning approach also has its advantages. Despite the learner's efforts and the use of appropriate methodologies, understanding the peculiarities of the human mind is crucial for successful language acquisition. Pedagogical methods are useful, but self-directed learning requires an understanding of the mechanisms of memory and perception. Effective learning depends on the synergy between human capabilities and teaching methods, necessitating the exploration and application of the best self-directed learning techniques that correspond to how the brain absorbs new information.

Keywords: Foreign language acquisition; Natural learning; Conscious learning; Implicit learning; Explicit learning; Pedagogical methods; Self-directed learning.

1. Introduction

The language has two forms of mastery: spoken and written. When a person speaks their native language, they acquire it orally within their family and then continue this process in school at a certain age.

Klein, W. (1986) *Language learning involves the acquisition of one language, often monolingual, by a child. This is the most extensively researched form of language learning. In Western European societies, bilingual FL occurs when a child learns two languages in parallel. However, there are also important factors for second language acquisition, such as the learner's initial language lack and the acquisition of multiple languages.*[1]

Whether the language is a native or foreign, academic study under a teacher's guidance is necessary for literary mastery. These reasons lead us to believe that the acquisition of the native language occurs in two stages: first, through oral instruction in a family setting, and then through written and grammatical instruction in school, under the guidance and instructions of teachers. Note that the first stage involves unconsciously acquiring the language, while the second involves conscious learning, highlighting the distinction between natural language acquisition and deliberate language learning.

Acquiring a foreign language can primarily occur in two stages, like learning a native language, but only if the learner resides and works in a foreign-language environment, such as a community within their home or workplace. Alternatively, if they live abroad, they may begin to acquire the foreign language through natural, unconscious language acquisition. For those who do not have a foreign-language environment, the intensive option for language acquisition remains in school or in a course under the guidance of a teacher, also known as deliberate language learning. The intensive

option has the advantage of allowing the learner to quickly delve into the nuances of the language, but it also has a drawback, which consists of the lower efficiency of acquiring the foreign language compared to its acquisition through natural means.

In addition to the learner's own efforts, acquiring a foreign language necessitates the use of appropriate educational tools and methodologies, but this alone is not sufficient. Teachers apply pedagogy, a science, to the process of teaching learners, which includes foreign language instruction. However, understanding the capabilities and peculiarities of the human mind is essential for acquiring a foreign language. Independently learning a foreign language without a teacher precludes the application of pedagogical methods. Therefore, the need to know how we best perceive and remember foreign language knowledge remains of paramount importance.

The main issues with foreign language learning are the effectiveness of language acquisition, maintenance, and improvement. Solving these problems requires understanding the mechanisms of learning and acquiring a foreign language. The conclusion is that understanding the human mind and its rational use are key to effective foreign language acquisition, regardless of the presence of pedagogical support. Therefore, it is important to research and apply the best self-directed learning techniques that correspond to the ways in which the brain most effectively perceives and remembers new information. In other words, we seek the points of contact between the human mind's capabilities to perceive and acquire foreign languages, and the methods and techniques for imparting foreign language knowledge, to ensure a synergy between human abilities to acquire a foreign language and the methods and techniques for teaching it.

2. Analysis of Matrix of Methods and Techniques for Learning a Foreign Language

The matrix of methods and techniques for learning a foreign language provides a detailed overview of various approaches to acquiring a foreign language. The

matrix categorizes these methods into implicit and explicit learning, shedding light on both unconscious and conscious learning strategies. This analysis examines each element of the matrix, exploring their roles and implications in the language learning process. (Table 1)

Table 1

Kostadinov's Matrix of Foreign Language Learning Methods and Techniques		
Language acquisition method	Implicit learning	Explicit teaching and learning
Method of language acquisition	Unconscious learning	Conscious learning
Grammar acquisition	Unconscious absorption	Deliberate learning
Listening comprehension	Listening to speeches and audio materials	Translating audio and written foreign texts.
Extensive reading comprehension	Reading for pleasure texts for graded readers and expanding general vocabulary.	Building a rich vocabulary and memorizing new words and phrases.
Intensive reading comprehension	Deep understanding of elaborate text, focusing on meaning and details.	Analysis of grammatical structures and lexical elements in the text.
Passive vocabulary acquisition	Multistage acquisition of foreign words. Learners are able to understand what they listen to and read.	Planning and measuring the number of foreign words to learn within a lesson; Planning and measuring repetition of vocabulary
Speaking and writing in a foreign language.	Verbal and written translations into foreign languages without use of a dictionary.	Verbal and written translations into foreign languages with use of a dictionary.
Active vocabulary acquisition	Unconscious enhancement of a foreign language active vocabulary with high proficiency words through listening and reading comprehension.	Conscious enhancement of a foreign language active vocabulary by deliberate speaking and writing using high proficiency words.
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- **Method of Language Acquisition**

Ellis, R., Loewen, S., Erlam, R. (2006) *Implicit knowledge is intuitively aware and accessible through automatic processing, while explicit knowledge is consciously aware and available through controlled processing. Explicit knowledge may be linked to metalinguistic labels, and these two types of knowledge are not mutually exclusive. For instance, linguists can formulate explicit rules based on their implicit knowledge of a language.*[2]

Implicit Learning: This method involves acquiring language skills without conscious effort. People often associate this method with a naturalistic environment, where learners encounter the language in use through conversations, media, and immersion in a language setting. This type of learning is gradual and mirrors the way children acquire their first language, relying on contextual cues and repeated exposure to internalize language patterns. Attention, in synergy with interest and curiosity towards the studied material, drives the most effective acquisition of the foreign language.

Explicit Teaching and Learning: Conversely, explicit learning involves deliberate instructions and conscious effort. Learners engage in structured lessons focusing on specific language rules, vocabulary, and usage. This method is systematic and often includes classroom activities, textbooks, and formal exercises designed to reinforce understanding and proper language usage. The main advantage is the ability to grasp the most difficult grammatical features quickly and easily. The two methods, implicit and explicit, should not be opposed to each other but rather embraced as mutually complementary.

- **Method of Language Acquisition**

Krashen, S. (1982) *The acquisition-learning distinction is a fundamental concept that suggests that adults can develop competence in a second language*

through two distinct methods. The first method is language acquisition, which is a subconscious process like children's development of their first language. Acquired competence is a result of this subconscious process, with grammar and errors feeling right or wrong. The second method is language learning, which involves conscious knowledge of a second language, its rules, and being aware of them. This distinction may not be unique to second language acquisition, as we may learn small parts of our first language in school, such as the who/whom distinction. However, the acquisition-learning hypothesis suggests that adults can access the same natural language acquisition device that children use, and that the ability to "pick-up" languages does not disappear at puberty. Error correction, while not having a significant impact on subconscious acquisition, is thought to be useful for conscious learning.[3]

Unconscious Learning: Unconscious learning occurs naturally, without the learner's active intention to learn. It happens through passive acquisition, often in an informal setting. Examples include learning new vocabulary by listening to native speakers or understanding grammatical structures through repeated exposure. This method leverages the brain's natural ability to recognize patterns and make sense of new information without explicit instructions. Unconscious acquisition obtains foreign language information aurally through reading, examining picture dictionaries, or watching videos that visually demonstrate the pronunciation of new words and phrases alongside visual representation, which aids in understanding their meaning.

Conscious Learning: On the other hand, conscious learning is deliberate and methodical. Learners actively focus on studying the language, often through formal education and structured practice. This method involves memorization, practical exercises, and

a clear understanding of grammar and vocabulary rules. It is goal-oriented, with learners setting specific objectives for their language acquisition. It primarily consists of grammar exercises under the guidance of a teacher who explains grammatical features and rules.

- **Listening**

McKay, I. (2024) *Language learners must master the crucial skill of listening, as it is central to real-world language use. Even in structured classroom environments, it is essential to practice listening skills to understand culturally shared conversations. Even fluency in reading doesn't guarantee understanding in casual or quick conversations. To effectively use a language, learners need to practice listening skills. Building listening skills allows access to various materials for learning about the language and its culture, enabling them to make the most of TV shows, YouTube videos, and music.*[4]

Implicit Learning: Listening to speeches and audio materials allows learners to naturally acquire the sounds, rhythms, and structures of the language. This method helps develop language listening skills, improve pronunciation, and understand spoken language in various contexts. It prioritizes exposure over comprehension, believing that repeated listening will lead to gradual acquisition.

Explicit Learning: In explicit learning, active speaking and communication practice complement listening skills. Learners engage in conversations, practice dialogues, and participate in speaking exercises to reinforce their listening skills. This approach combines passive listening with active usage, ensuring that learners not only understand but can also speak the language accurately.

- **Reading**

Akbar, F. (2014). *Reading is a crucial aspect of language learning, as it helps learners comprehend and develop their speaking skills. Vocabulary knowledge is essential for effective communication, and reading is the best way to learn new words. Extensive reading helps learners understand contexts and build vocabulary, which are essential elements for advancing speaking skills. Reading habits enable learners to guess the meanings of words and phrases from context, promoting their speaking performance. Extensive reading also enhances other language skills such as writing and speaking. By integrating speaking and reading skills, students can strengthen their understanding of reading material, identify any issues they may have, and apply the information they have read into authentic speaking practice, ultimately improving their fluency.*[5]

Implicit Learning through Reading: Reading texts provides a passive way to encounter the language. By observing the context of words and phrases, learners can grasp their meaning and usage without explicit guidance. This method encourages the natural expansion of vocabulary and familiarity with different writing styles and genres.

Explicit Learning through Reading: Writing various types of texts is the active counterpart to reading. By practicing writing, learners apply what they have read and absorbed. This helps reinforce their

understanding of grammar, vocabulary, and syntax. Writing exercises often include composing essays, reports, and creative works, each of which reinforces different aspects of language usage. It also entails learning explicit grammar.

- **Intensive Reading**

Intensive reading is a method that involves in-depth study of a text to understand its literary or linguistic meaning. It involves concentration and careful detail, aiming to identify answers to reading comprehension questions. It can be used for skimming, scanning, and sentence concatenation. Intensive reading involves deconstruction of sentences, analyzing words, phrases, and collocations to extract the essence and meaning of the text. Goals include understanding the gist and subject matter, improving grammar and vocabulary, and understanding the author's thought. The focus is on the language used, rather than the text itself.[6]

Implicit Learning: Intensive reading focuses on a deep understanding of complex texts. Learners pay attention to meaning and details without explicitly analyzing grammatical structures. This method encourages engagement with content, fostering a deeper evaluation of the language and its nuances.

Explicit Learning: In contrast, explicit, intensive reading involves analyzing the text's grammatical structures and lexical elements. Students analyze sentences to understand the rules and patterns at play. This analytical approach guarantees their understanding of the fundamental mechanics of language, enabling them to apply it to their own usage.

- **Extensive Reading**

Extensive reading is a casual, enjoyable method of gaining general understanding on a topic through reading long texts and referring to supporting study material. This approach helps improve reading fluency and speed by selecting easy, interesting, and amusing books. Students can choose the book or material they prefer, focusing on topics that match their interests. There is no follow-up discussion in class, allowing students to learn without the need for class discussion. Extensive reading encourages reading habits for pleasure and makes students voracious readers, regardless of their understanding of each word. It also allows students to read material according to their reading speed and capability.[6]

Implicit Learning: Extensive reading involves reading for pleasure, which helps expand overall vocabulary and understanding. Learners read various texts at a comfortable level, improving fluency, and reinforcing previously learned vocabulary and structures. The goal is to enjoy the content while passively enhancing language skills.

Explicit Learning: Building vocabulary through targeted study of new words is an active aspect of extensive reading. Learners use dictionaries, flashcards, and word lists to memorize new vocabulary. This method ensures that they not only encounter new words but also retain them for future active use.

- **Conclusion**

The matrix of methods and techniques for learning a foreign language demonstrates the complexity and

multidimensionality of language education. By combining implicit and explicit methods, as well as conscious and unconscious strategies, learners can achieve comprehensive and profound language acquisition. Each approach has its own unique advantages and, when used together, can provide well-rounded and effective results.

Language learning involves the acquisition of a foreign language through two stages: natural and conscious learning. Natural acquisition is more effective, while intensive learning has its advantages. Understanding the human mind's peculiarities is crucial for successful language acquisition. Pedagogical methods are useful, but self-directed learning requires an understanding of memory and perception mechanisms. Effective learning depends on the synergy between human capabilities and teaching methods, necessitating the exploration and application of the best self-directed learning techniques. The matrix of methods and techniques for learning a foreign language categorizes these methods into implicit and explicit learning. Implicit learning involves acquiring language skills without conscious effort, mirroring the way children acquire their first language through conversations, media, and immersion in a language setting. Explicit teaching and learning involve deliberate instructions and conscious effort, engaging learners in structured lessons focusing on specific language rules, vocabulary, and usage. Both methods should be embraced as mutually complementary.

Language learning is a process that involves two distinct methods: subconscious language acquisition and conscious language learning. Implicit learning occurs naturally, often through passive exposure to foreign language information, while conscious learning is deliberate and methodical. Listening is a crucial skill for language learners, and explicit learning involves active speaking and communication practice. Reading is another essential aspect of language learning, as it helps learners comprehend and develop speaking skills. Implicit learning through reading provides a passive way to encounter the language, while explicit learning in-

volves writing various types of texts to reinforce understanding of grammar, vocabulary, and syntax. Intensive reading involves in-depth study of a text to understand its literary or linguistic meaning, while extensive reading is a casual, enjoyable method of gaining general understanding on a topic. Both methods help expand vocabulary and understanding, while also enhancing fluency and retaining previously learned vocabulary. The acquisition-learning hypothesis suggests that adults can access the same natural language acquisition device as children, and error correction is useful for conscious learning.

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THE ROLE OF KAZAKH LEGENDS IN THE LINGUISTIC PICTURE OF THE WORLD

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ABSTRACT

Systematization of Kazakh legends, highlighting their differences from other folklore genres, evaluating them from the point of view of the history, criticism, theory of literature were analyzed in this article. The place of legends in the linguistic picture of the world is determined. From the legends considered mainly from the point of view of literary criticism, we have distinguished our object of study, that is, texts analyzed from the point of view of language. Teaching the language of legends should not be limited to conducting a linguistic analysis of the language units used in it. One of the main tasks of the study is the analysis of linguistic and cultural units in legends for the student.

Keywords: worldview, cognitive cognition, a picture of the world, legend, anthropocentrism, linguoculturology, national consciousness, ethnolinguistics.

Introduction. Each nation has its own culture, history, traditions, worldview, and its own values. Although nature and the environment are common for humanity, each people lives in different places and in different ways. Even if a person of any nationality utters the same word, in his mind it can have a different cognitive structure. Despite the fact that each nation understands the elements of a special structure common to all nations in different ways, it creates its own national image and picture of the world. Therefore, a special place in linguistics is occupied by cognitive linguistics, a new direction that studies the relationship between language, culture and the world, their influence on each other.

Relevance of the study. Culture, language, history and society have a great influence on the formation of the picture of the world. Because the language is constantly connected with society, the social environment, the centuries-old history of the people, ethnic knowledge, life experience passed down from generation to generation, spiritual essence, traditions, customs, culture.

Although the knowledge of the human race is the same in all peoples, there are also points that differ when it comes to a separate ethnic group. Throughout life, a person fixes his knowledge in words, while knowing the world. The totality of this knowledge, presented in a linguistic form, is called the linguistic picture of the world. Features of the linguistic picture of the world and its nature depend on language, since language is the most important way of forming a person's knowledge of the world. The linguistic picture of the world reflects not only human ideas about the universe, but also national views on life, traditions, beliefs.

One of the main principles in creating a linguistic picture of the world is the anthropocentric position. In any era, science, education, art, culture – the goal that everyone set for themselves was to get to know a person from the point of view of his experience and values. All various actions in this world are inextricably linked with a person and his personality traits. The importance of studying the anthropocentric in the enumeration of the totality of human knowledge about the whole world is enormous.

Anthropocentricity in linguistics has long been a revelation in the modern scientific community, its facets and secrets are analyzed in detail. The main position of this scientific direction, which has been developing rapidly over the past half century, is to consider language in unity with human existence. Today, on the basis of anthropological linguistics, a number of scientific directions have been formed, interconnected and closely connected with each other. In particular, they are: sociolinguistics, ethnolinguistics, psycholinguistics, linguoculturology, cognitive linguistics and paleolinguistics [1]. These disciplines come to life as a result of their sociability and integration with other branches of Science and are considered within the framework of extralinguistics.

Methodology. To identify the factors contributing to the development of the Kazakh legends in the linguistic picture of the world, and to consider the problems in a systematic way. Differentiation in relation to language policy and language strategy based on their sources. Methods of interpretation, intuitive assessment, and linguistic analysis were used.

Discussion and results. Today, one of the only principles that determine the trends in the development of linguistic science is the manifestation of language in an anthropocentric direction. Thus, by studying the language in connection with the ethnic group, its thinking, worldview, common sense, national culture, it creates a linguistic picture of the world. The problem of the linguistic picture of the world in the anthropocentric direction was discussed in Russian linguistics by B.A.Serebrennikov, E.S.Kubryakova, V.I.Postovalova, V.N.Telia, A.A.Ufimtseva, A.Vezhbitskaya, V.G.Kolshansky, Yu.Karaulov, V.Maslov, and in Kazakh linguistics by A.Kaidar, M.Kopylenko, E.Zhanpeisov, K.Khusain, N.Uali the object of research of scientists was B.Kaliev, Zh.Mankeeva, G.Smagulova, G.Sagidolda, A.Islam, B.Tleuberdiev, E.Orazalieva, B.Akberdieva, G.Snasapova, K.Zhamanbayeva, A.Almautova, K.Kurkebayev, A.Amirbekova, G.Tuyakbayev, K.Saryshova, A.Abasilov and others.

Language is the collective name of such spiritual heritage as a text, a work of art, a poem, a fairy tale, a